

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE SKILLS OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING

D.B.Toreshov

Assistant teacher of **KARAKALPAK STATE UNIVERSITY NAMED AFTER BERDAKH**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11367156>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 21th May 2024

Accepted: 27th May 2024

Online: 28th May 2024

KEYWORDS

Technology, modern concepts, self-education, optimization.

ABSTRACT

The mentioned methodological aspects of preparing students for creative development have a number of undoubted merits. Conducting contests and Olympiads at the end of the discipline are an additional external motivation of creative activity, as well as form the ability to creatively apply the acquired knowledge in stressful situations.

One of the studies of improving the quality of professional education training can be considered the improvement of the system of methodological support of the educational process of educational institutions, development on the basis of modern technologies, combining traditional and modern methods of organizing the educational process, embodied in progressive ideas on the basis of scientific and technical achievements.

Taking into account modern concepts and innovative technologies, manifested in all spheres of human life, the requirements to the level of professional training of university graduates, to self-education, the ability to think independently, optimize their activities, make non-trivial decisions have increased.

Education is the main priority and the main indicator of development in all civilized countries of the world. Obtaining higher education has always been, remains and will be one of the most important things in a person's life, especially in the modern world with its fierce competition in the labor market.

Higher education, as a designation of the level of education, means the upper level of professional education in the three-level system (after secondary general or vocational education) and includes a set of systematized knowledge, skills and practical skills that allow to solve theoretical and practical problems in the professional profile.

The processes of modernization of the republican system of higher education impose new requirements to the content of educational activity of higher education institutions and determine the need to train specialists with innovation-oriented professional thinking, actively participating in the development of domestic production.

In this regard, the content and technologies of higher education are focused on the definition and formation of a set of special knowledge, skills and abilities of future specialists related to the successful realization of professional functions. It is these knowledge and skills

that are the main professional activities aimed at creating high-tech products, which determines the growth of the quality of life of the population.

Despite the fact that pedagogical science has accumulated extensive material for the formation of creative skills and skills of students in the process of design design, the above problem is underdeveloped.

The existing shortcomings in the professional training of design specialists reveal the following contradictions:

- between the need of society in the innovative development of modern domestic design design and traditional approaches to the professional training of specialists in the field of design.

- between the need to implement modern special training, providing competence, creative activity of future designers and established approaches to professional training;

- between the high requirements of the market of educational services to the quality and content of specialist training and the lack of a scientifically substantiated system of formation of creative skills of students.

These contradictions allowed us to formulate the research problem, which consists in the scientific and theoretical substantiation of the system of formation of creative skills of students in the process of design design in the conditions of professional activity, providing the improvement of the quality of professional training, development of innovation-oriented professional thinking, necessary for future labor activity in the field of design.

For the formation of creative skills of students in the process of design design requires the development of practice-oriented, art-developmental and competence-based approaches to the training of future specialists in the field of design.[1]

Formation of creative skills and skills of students will be effective if the respubla medethodical system, focused on the formation of creative skills, as well as creative qualities of personality: training in enlarged blocks - modules; apply tasks that form professional thinking and aimed at mastering innovative activity in the field of design; strengthen the integration of disciplines in the learning process; manage the joint search activity, carrying out in the framework of subject-subject relations.

The study of the whole direction in the psychology of creativity, known as creativity, was conducted by the following scientists: J.Guilford, V.Smith, N.G.Frolov, E.G.Yudina and others. J.Guilford believes that creativity and creative potential can be defined as a set of abilities and other traits that contribute to successful creative thinking.

Also great theoretical and practical work on the development of creativity of students is carried out by such teachers as: G.A.Khusainova, L.K.Toporkova.

Priority need of the student (conditioned both internally - aspiration to creativity, and externally - the order of the labor market for a specialist, ready for innovative activity) is the need to develop their creative skills and skills, creativity, especially in terms of professional creativity.

Considering the dominant methodological approaches in modern higher education, we have revealed the components that hinder the modernization of the system of higher professional education.

First of all, it is the absence of an independent discipline in the structure of most working curricula, which would give students the necessary knowledge about the nature of creativity, the origins of creative activity, ways to activate creative thinking. Within the framework of many disciplines of the curriculum teachers give students knowledge about the basic organization of creative activity, methods and techniques of creative search, form the necessary skills for students. But this does not happen in a systematic way.

Secondly, the lack of systematic organization of educational and creative activity during the entire period of professional development of a specialist in higher education, which would meet the requirements for the development of personality creativity, namely, the lack of rigid restrictions on the time and degree of participation, professional orientation of the creative process, the presence of an appropriate microclimate.

But against the background of the above problems there is a need to create conditions for pedagogical support for the development of creative skills and skills of students and their creative self-development on the basis of using the effect of creative competitions and Olympiads, when in solving creative problems students identify new problems in the studied subject area. That is, the student's activity in creative mastering of the academic discipline after the competition or Olympiad does not stop, but acquires an intrinsically motivational character, which allows him to acquire the necessary creative skills.[3].

Competitions and Olympiads allow to identify students aimed at creativity, to organize in the future their collective activity within the framework of competitive microgroups under the guidance of a teacher, as well as to determine the level of development of creative skills of students.

Corrective measures of organization of independent work determine the success of preserving the manifested indicator of creative activity after the competition or Olympiad, such as:

- Providing consultations on solving non-standard creative problems, including in interactive mode with the use of information technologies;
- Provision of methodical materials containing creative tasks in the academic discipline with different levels of creativity, assuming the possibility of students to go beyond the limits outlined in the condition in the process of their discussion;
- Solution by students of creative competitive tasks in distant mode with the use of information technologies

In order to form creative skills and skills of students in practical classes should provide familiarization of students with the main approaches to solving non-standard problems in the discipline, project assignments, brainstorming, business games, other types of activities that require skills and skills of creative activity.

Conducting competitions and Olympiads at the end of the discipline are an additional external motivation of creative activity, as well as form the ability to creatively apply knowledge in stressful situations.

The above methodological aspects of preparing students for creative development have a number of undoubted merits, among which the following possibilities can be noted:

1. To model the system of problem situations aimed at the formation of creative skills of a design specialist, oriented innovative projects;
2. To prepare the student for the real creative activity of a particular struggle;
3. To acquaint the student with the most effective methods of organization of own creative activity in conditions of collective and to use these methods taking into account regularities of professional formation of the specialist;
4. To form creative skills and skills simultaneously recognizable number of students by spreading knowledge about professional creativity and skills of creative problem solving to the whole student team in the process of joint activities in traditional forms of training.

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